

EFFECTS OF LEADERSHIP STYLES OF SCHOOL HEADS TO THE SCHOOL CLIMATE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR COACHING AND MENTORING PROGRAM

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Effects of Leadership Styles of School Heads to the School Climate of Public Elementary Schools in Third Congressional District of Quezon: Basis for Coaching and Mentoring Program

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Abstract

This study focuses on the relationship between leadership styles adopted by school heads and the resultant school climate in public elementary schools. The aim is to provide insights into how different leadership approaches influence the overall atmosphere, culture, and effectiveness of educational institutions. Through a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from a diverse sample of public elementary schools, incorporating surveys, interviews, and observations. This study emphasizes the importance of nurturing supportive, inclusive, and growth-oriented school environments, aligning with principles of transformational leadership. Findings underscore the critical role of school heads' leadership styles in shaping the organizational culture and climate within public elementary schools. The ANOVA results revealed no significant difference in the perception of leadership styles among school heads, teachers, and parents, suggesting that despite minor variations in mean scores, these differences lack statistical significance. The study highlights the perceived significance of school heads' leadership styles in shaping a positive school climate across various stakeholder groups and underscores the need for continued emphasis on leadership development to enhance educational outcomes and stakeholder satisfaction. The proposed Leadership Styles Intervention Program for Public Elementary Schools aims to empower school leaders to create and maintain supportive climates that prioritize student success and well-being, promoting thriving learning communities.

Keywords: *elementary schools, intervention, leadership styles, school climate, transformational leadership*

Introduction

Leadership stands as the cornerstone of any organization, wielding the power to dictate its triumphs or setbacks. It serves as the catalyst for schools to progress, flourish, or falter. Within every organization, leaders fulfill specific roles and tasks to ensure operational efficiency and enhance overall performance. Their manner of executing these responsibilities and steering the organization forward constitutes their leadership style (Oyetunyi, 2016). This style encapsulates how leaders lead, varying from those who prioritize task completion over interpersonal relationships to those who emphasize rapport with subordinates over job execution.

Undoubtedly, effective leadership is imperative for optimizing school performance and engaging all stakeholders. Public school heads, commonly referred to as school principals, play a pivotal role in the holistic development of schools and communities alike. Serving as both instructional leaders and administrative managers (Republic Act 9155), their leadership styles shape the governance and operation of their respective schools. The chosen leadership style significantly influences the collaboration and rapport between the school head and the school community, thereby shaping the overall social atmosphere within schools.

Furthermore, school heads bear the responsibility of fostering positive learning, social, and physical environments within schools. They spearhead initiatives for change and continually seek opportunities to enhance the school climate (UNICEF, 2021). As such, effective and efficient leadership styles are indispensable for nurturing a conducive school climate. The Department of Education's vision (2013) aims to empower school heads to unleash their leadership potential and cultivate a positive school climate, echoing the principles outlined in Republic Act 9155, the Governance of Basic Education of 2001. Section 7 of Chapter 1 of RA 9155 delineates the powers, duties, and functions of school heads at the school level, emphasizing their accountability for fostering a conducive environment for teaching and learning (Republic Act 9155).

At the international level, research on educational leadership has highlighted the significance of leadership styles in shaping school culture and climate. Studies conducted in various countries have demonstrated that transformational leadership, characterized by vision-setting, motivation, and support for innovation, tends to correlate positively with positive school climates and improved student achievement (Leithwood et al., 2018; Hallinger & Heck, 2018). Conversely, autocratic or laissez-faire leadership styles have been associated with negative outcomes such as teacher burnout, low morale, and diminished student performance (Goddard et al., 2016; Mulford & Silins, 2019).

On a national level, the Philippines has witnessed a growing interest in educational leadership research, particularly concerning its impact on school effectiveness and improvement. Studies conducted in Philippine educational settings have explored the relationship between leadership styles and various school outcomes, including student achievement, teacher satisfaction, and organizational effectiveness (Cruz, 2017; Mendoza, 2015). However, there remains a paucity of research specifically focusing on the Third Congressional District of Quezon, limiting our understanding of how leadership styles influence school climate within this unique local context.

Locally, the Third Congressional District of Quezon encompasses a diverse range of communities, each with its own socio-economic

challenges and educational needs. Understanding the leadership dynamics within public elementary schools in this district is essential for designing targeted interventions that address the specific challenges faced by educators, students, and communities. By investigating the effects of leadership styles on school climate in this local setting, this research aims to provide actionable insights that inform the development of coaching and mentoring programs tailored to the needs of school leaders in the district.

In light of the foregoing, this study seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on educational leadership by examining the relationship between leadership styles of school heads and school climate in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. By identifying the leadership practices that foster positive school climates, this research aims to inform the design and implementation of coaching and mentoring programs that support school leaders in enhancing educational outcomes and promoting student success.

Research Questions

The primary goal of this study was to ascertain and evaluate the effects of leadership styles of school heads on the school climate of public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon. It specifically sought to answer the following research problems:

1. What are the different leadership style practices of the public elementary school heads in the third congressional district of Quezon as assessed by:
 - 1.1. school heads;
 - 1.2. teachers; and
 - 1.3. parents?
2. Is there a significant difference in the leadership style practices of the public elementary school heads in the third congressional district of Quezon as assessed by:
 - 2.1. school heads;
 - 2.2. teachers; and
 - 2.3. parents?
3. What is the school climate existing in the public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon as assessed by:
 - 3.1. school heads;
 - 3.2. teachers; and
 - 3.3. parents?
4. What is the effect of the school heads' leadership style/s on the school climate in the public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon as assessed by:
 - 4.1. school heads;
 - 4.2. teachers; and
 - 4.3. parents?
5. What leadership intervention program for implementation of coaching and mentoring could be formulated for the school heads based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized descriptive research design to systematically obtain information about the effects of leadership styles of school heads to the school climate in the public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon. Thus, to answer the main and sub-problems of the study, a validated self-constructed questionnaire was used as the research instrument. The questionnaire includes indicators of leadership styles exercised by the school heads, items that determined the existing school climate in the public elementary schools, and the effects of the leadership styles to the school climate of the public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon. To ensure the validity of the data to be gathered, the researcher likewise applied a triangulation approach wherein teachers and parent-stakeholders of the respective school head respondents were asked to answer the same research questionnaire. The results of the data gathered from both school heads and teacher-respondents were compared and analyzed.

Respondents

This research involved a complete enumeration of 213 public elementary school heads in the third congressional district of Quezon as respondents of the study. To ensure the validity of the responses in terms of the existing school climate in the locale as well as the effects of the leadership styles of school heads on the school climate, the researcher distributed the research tool in proportional random sampling defined as the availability of the teachers and parents from the central school in the third congressional district of Quezon. The tables below show the exact number of school heads as the target population of the study and the teachers and parents from the central school in the third congressional district of Quezon.

Table 1. *Designation of Public Elementary School Heads*

<i>Designation</i>	<i>Number</i>
Principal IV	2
Principal III	23
Principal II	10
Principal I	56
Head Teacher III	23
Head Teacher II	16
Head Teacher I	47
Teacher-In-Charge	35
Officer-In-Charge	1
Total	213

Table 2. *Number of Teachers and Parents per District from Central School*

<i>District</i>	<i>No. of teachers</i>	<i>No. of Respondents of Teachers and Parents</i>
Agdangan Central Elementary School	33	14
Buenavista Central Elementary School	32	14
Catanauan Central School	90	38
General luna Central Elementary School	39	17
Macalelon Central Elementary School	41	17
Mulanay Central Elementary School	68	29
Padre Burgos Central Elementary School	37	16
Pitogo Central Elementary School	35	15
San Andres Central Elementary School	31	13
San Francisco Central Elementary School	40	17
San Narciso Central Elementary School	52	22
Unisan Central Elementary School	39	17
	N=537	229

Instruments

The research instrument used in gathering the needed information was a researcher-made survey questionnaire which was subjected to validation before the actual distribution. The first part of the instrument consists of items that aimed to determine the different leadership style/s practices of the public elementary school heads as to indicators 1 and 3 for transformational leadership; indicators 2, 9, and 15 for democratic leadership; indicators 5 and 7 for collaborative leadership; indicator 11 for transactional leadership; indicators 4 and 6 for delegative leadership style; and indicators 8, 12, and 13 for servant leadership; indicators 10 and 14 for instructional leadership style. The second part consists of items that aimed to answer the school climate existing in the public elementary schools; for open climate are indicators 1, 2, 3, and 4; for autonomous climate are indicators 5, 6, and 7; controlled climate are indicators 8 and 9; familiar climate are indicators 10, 11, and 12; and closed climate are indicators 13, 14, and 15. Finally, the third part sought to answer the effect of the school heads' leadership style/s on the school climate in the public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon.

To determine the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire it was pre-tested in 30 individuals who were not respondents of the study. To analyze the results of the validation, the Cronbach Alpha was used in the process. The research adviser and the statistician were informed of the findings for them to take any additional actions that may be necessary. Finally, the comments and suggestions of the research adviser and the statistician were considered before the final distribution of the questionnaire.

Procedure

The researcher-made questionnaire was crafted considering the specific problems in Chapter I. A group of experts in the field of educational management reviewed the self-made questionnaire for further development as to its content. The feedback and recommendations provided by these experts were considered and incorporated in the revised research questionnaire. After considering all the remarks and recommendations, it was presented to the experts who reexamined the research questionnaire. After its approval by the experts, the research questionnaire was pre-implemented for reliability and validity test. The statistician was informed of the results and given the opportunity to take any additional action that may be necessary.

After gathering the needed data through a survey, the responses were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher. The results served as bases in formulating the conclusions and recommendations of the study.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the respondents' responses were treated statistically, tabulated, and analyzed to arrive at a conclusion and recommendations for the study. To solve the problem posed in this study, the researcher used the following statistical tools:

To determine the different leadership styles of the school heads, the researcher used weighted mean;

To determine the significant difference in leadership styles of the school heads, the researcher used one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA);

To determine the existing school climate, weighted mean is also used.

To determine the effect of the school heads' leadership style/s on the school climate, research also used weighted mean.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that the respondents' participation in sharing their responses in the survey was voluntary while taking into account their right to privacy. A consent form was additionally made available for the respondents to sign. Likewise, the participants were assured of their anonymity and the anonymous presentation of results, as well as their freedom to withdraw at any moment without giving a reason. The author of every source and piece of information used in this study were also acknowledged and properly cited by the researcher.

Results and Discussion

The information the researcher obtained to address the issues raised in the Statement of the Problem (SOP) is presented in this section. This information was gathered using the study's quantitative instruments, from which these data were extracted types of leadership styles of school heads, existing school climate, and the effects of leadership styles to the school climate of public elementary schools.

Part I. Different Leadership Styles practices of the public elementary school heads

Table 3.1. *Leadership Styles Practices by Public Elementary School as perceived by School Heads*

Question	As Assessed by School Heads					Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. accepts criticism with grace.	90	95	27	1	0	4.29	0.70	Always Practiced
2. is "hands-on" during professional development.	68	110	35	0	0	4.15	0.68	Often Practiced
3. treats subordinate as an individual with unique skills and talents.	40	128	45	0	0	3.98	0.63	Often Practiced
4. is knowledgeable about best teaching practices.	54	127	32	0	0	4.10	0.63	Often Practiced
5. help people take advantage of opportunities to learn new skills.	65	129	19	0	0	4.22	0.59	Always Practiced
6. has a willingness to tap into the expertise of those around him or her.	70	114	29	0	0	4.19	0.66	Often Practiced
7. create credible processes for collaborating.	49	127	37	0	0	4.06	0.63	Often Practiced
8. elicits input from all stakeholders.	64	123	26	0	0	4.18	0.63	Often Practiced
9. cultivates positive relationships among faculty members.	49	123	41	0	0	4.04	0.65	Often Practiced
10. visit classes regularly to observe teaching and learning.	35	137	41	0	0	3.97	0.60	Often Practiced
11. provides recognition to faculty and staff for a job well done.	47	129	37	0	0	4.05	0.63	Often Practiced
12. encourages others to grow in their role.	71	123	19	0	0	4.24	0.60	Always Practiced
13. presence demands aspects.	45	140	28	0	0	4.08	0.58	Often Practiced
14. solve issues related to discipline to maximize instructional time.	28	146	39	0	0	3.95	0.56	Often Practiced
15. makes others feel valued.	45	140	28	0	0	4.08	0.58	Often Practiced
Composite Mean						4.10	0.62	Often Practiced

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Always Practiced; 3.41 - 4.20, Often Practiced; 2.61 - 3.40, Sometimes Practiced; 1.81 - 2.60, Rarely Practiced; 1.00 - 1.80, Never Practiced

The table presents a comprehensive overview of the perceived leadership styles and practices of public elementary school heads, as assessed by school heads. The data are summarized in terms of mean scores, verbal interpretations, and ranks for each question, along with an overall mean score. Overall, the data indicate that the school heads are generally viewed as influential leaders, with an overall mean score of 4.10, which falls under the verbal interpretation of "Often Practiced." This suggests that the majority of the leadership practices assessed in the survey are perceived to be regularly implemented by the school heads.

Several specific leadership practices stand out as particularly strong: "Accepting criticism with grace" tops the list with the highest mean score of 4.29, indicating that this practice is consistently observed by the respondents; "Encouraging others to grow in their role" follows closely behind with a mean score of 4.24, also falling under the category of "Always Practiced"; "helps people to take advantage of opportunities to learn new skills" is another notable strength, with a mean score of 4.22. "Encouraging a willingness to tap into the expertise of those around them" and "eliciting input from all stakeholders" also receive high mean scores of 4.19 and 4.18, respectively, indicating these practices are commonly observed.

However, there are areas where improvement may be warranted: "Inspiring or motivating those whom they lead and treating subordinates as individuals with unique skills and talents" received mean scores of 3.98, which is slightly below the overall mean, suggesting these practices may not be as consistently implemented as others. Moreover, "making personal connections with all faculty

and staff” and “providing recognition for a job well done” also received mean scores of 4.06 and 4.04 respectively which are slightly below the overall mean, indicating there may be room for enhancement in these areas.

Being “solve issues related to discipline to maximize instructional time” received the lowest mean score of 3.95 among all the assessed practices, indicating that this aspect of leadership may not be as commonly practiced as others. The provided data offer valuable insights into how school heads perceive themselves regarding leadership qualities and practices. The mean scores, verbal interpretations, ranks, and leadership styles collectively show a comprehensive picture of the perceived effectiveness of school heads across various attributes. It is evident that certain qualities, such as “accepting criticism with grace”, “encouraging others to grow in their roles”, and “finding innovative solutions to long-standing problems”, are highly esteemed among school leaders. These attributes align closely with “transformational” and “servant” leadership styles, emphasizing fostering growth, innovation, and collaboration within educational settings. Effective leadership, as perceived by school heads, contributes to a positive school climate (Leithwood et al., 2019). Transformational leadership styles often correlate with better school climates.

Additionally, the data highlights the significance of democratic leadership practices, such as “eliciting input from stakeholders”, being ‘hands-on’ during professional development”, and “making others feel valued”. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of leadership approaches that prioritize empowerment, inclusivity, and continuous improvement in driving positive outcomes within schools. These insights are consistent with existing literature on educational leadership, which emphasizes the critical role of transformational, servant, and democratic leadership styles in promoting organizational effectiveness and enhancing student success (Leithwood et al., 2018; Day et al., 2020).

In summary, while the school heads are generally perceived as influential leaders who often practice key leadership behaviors, there are specific areas where further attention and development may be beneficial to enhance their overall leadership effectiveness and impact within the school community.

A related literature that supports the findings above include the study of Leithwood and Jantzi (2018) which explores the impact of different leadership practices on student achievement. Relatively, it emphasizes the importance of school leaders' ability to foster a positive school climate, build relationships, and provide instructional leadership. These aspects align closely with the leadership practices identified in the findings presented, such as accepting criticism with grace, encouraging others to grow, and finding innovative solutions to problems. Furthermore, Leithwood, Day, Sammons, Harris, and Hopkins (2016) found that effective school leadership positively correlates with school climate. They highlight the significance of leaders' abilities to create a shared vision, develop professional learning communities, and promote a culture of collaboration and trust among staff members. These findings support the importance of leadership practices such as making personal connections with faculty and staff, eliciting stakeholder input, and cultivating positive relationships among faculty members, as identified in the data.

Overall, both studies provide empirical evidence reinforcing the notion that effective leadership practices, as perceived by the school heads in the data, are essential for creating a conducive environment for student learning and overall school success.

Table 3.2. Leadership Style/s Practices of Public Elementary School Heads as perceived by Teachers

Question	As Assessed by Teachers					Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. accepts criticism with grace.	60	131	38	0	0	4.10	0.65	Often Practiced
2. is “hands-on” during professional development.	73	132	24	0	0	4.21	0.62	Always Practiced
3. treats subordinate as an individual with unique skills and talents.	91	115	23	0	0	4.30	0.64	Always Practiced
4. is knowledgeable about best teaching practices.	83	127	19	0	0	4.28	0.61	Always Practiced
5. help people take advantage of opportunities to learn new skills.	54	146	29	0	0	4.11	0.59	Often Practiced
6. has a willingness to tap into the expertise of those around him or her.	80	120	29	0	0	4.22	0.65	Always Practiced
7. create credible processes for collaborating.	69	134	26	0	0	4.19	0.62	Often Practiced
8. elicits input from all stakeholders.	40	157	32	0	0	4.03	0.56	Often Practiced
9. cultivates positive relationships among faculty members.	65	145	19	0	0	4.20	0.57	Often Practiced
10. visit classes regularly to observe teaching and learning.	71	134	24	0	0	4.21	0.61	Always Practiced
11. provides recognition to faculty and staff for a job well done.	74	138	17	0	0	4.25	0.58	Always Practiced
12. encourages others to grow in their role.	68	129	32	0	0	4.16	0.65	Often Practiced
13. presence demands aspects.	46	149	34	0	0	4.05	0.59	Often Practiced
14. solve issues related to discipline to maximize instructional time.	53	147	29	0	0	4.10	0.59	Often Practiced
15. makes others feel valued.	60	148	21	0	0	4.17	0.57	Often Practiced
Composite Mean						4.17	0.61	Often Practiced

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Always Practiced; 3.41 - 4.20, Often Practiced; 2.61 - 3.40, Sometimes Practiced; 1.81 - 2.60, Rarely Practiced; 1.00 - 1.80, Never Practiced

The study on the leadership styles and practices of public elementary school heads, as perceived by teachers, provides valuable insights into the effectiveness and prevalence of various leadership indicators. The mean scores for each indicator offer a nuanced understanding of the perceived importance and frequency of specific leadership practices among school heads.

Among the top-ranked indicators, “treats subordinate as an individual with unique skills and talents ” garnered the highest mean score of 4.30, indicating that this practice is consistently perceived as always practiced by school heads. This underscores the significance of building strong interpersonal relationships in educational leadership aligning with transformational leadership principles that emphasize building trust and rapport among team members. Following closely is the indicator of “knowledgeable about best teaching process”, with a mean score of 4.28, highlighting the importance of constructive feedback and openness to improvement which is crucial for fostering a culture of continuous improvement and professional growth.

Additionally, “provides recognition to faculty and staff for a job well done” also received a high mean score of 4.25, indicating a strong emphasis on professional development and mentorship within the school leadership. This suggests a commitment to fostering a culture of continuous learning and growth among faculty and staff.

Other indicators that received high mean scores include help people take advantage opportunities to learn new skills (mean score: 4.22) being "hands-on" during professional development and visit classes regularly to observe teaching and learning (mean score: 4.21). These scores reflect a focus on active engagement, creativity, and empowerment in leadership practices, implying the presence of democratic leadership practices that emphasize the importance of inclusive decision-making and collaboration in school leadership.

Additionally, indicators related to servant leadership, such as encouraging others to grow in their role (mean score: 4.16) and eliciting input from all stakeholders (mean score: 4.03), received notable mean scores, indicating a commitment to serving the needs of others and promoting collaboration and inclusivity. These results suggest that teachers view their school heads as leaders who prioritize serving the needs of and facilitating the development of their teachers, reflecting a commitment to empowering their subordinates.

Interestingly, while transformational leadership practices dominated the top rankings, there were notable mentions of delegative and transactional leadership elements among the practices. For instance, finding innovative solutions to long-standing problems and tapping into the expertise of others are indicative of delegation leadership, where leaders trust and empower their team members to take initiative and contribute their expertise. Additionally, providing recognition for a job well done aligns with transactional leadership principles, which emphasize rewarding desired behaviors and performance.

Coversely, it is also essential to acknowledge the indicators that received relatively lower mean scores, as they offer insights into areas where improvement may be needed or where certain leadership practices may be less familiar. Among the indicators with lower mean scores, providing recognition to faculty and staff for a job well done received a mean score of 4.03. While still indicating that this practice is often practiced, the slightly lower score suggests that there may be room for improvement in terms of acknowledging and appreciating the contributions of faculty and staff.

Another indicator with a relatively lower mean score is the presence demands aspects, which received a mean score of 4.05. This suggests that while still often practiced, there may be opportunities for school heads to personalize their approach to leadership further and recognize the diverse strengths and abilities of their team members.

By acknowledging the indicators with lower mean scores, educational leaders can identify areas for growth and development in their leadership practices. Addressing these areas can help improve teacher morale, job satisfaction, and overall organizational effectiveness, ultimately contributing to a more positive and productive school climate.

Overall, the study highlights the multifaceted nature of effective leadership in educational settings, encompassing aspects of transformational, servant, democratic, delegative, and transactional leadership. By embracing diverse leadership practices, school heads can create supportive and inclusive school climates conducive to teacher satisfaction and student success.

Table 3.3 presents the parents’ perception regarding the leadership style and practices of public elementary school heads. Overall, parents view the school heads positively, with notable strengths evident in various aspects of their leadership approach. Precisely the top five indicators such as creating credible processes for collaborating (Mean: 4.38), accepting criticism with grace (Mean: 4.33), encouraging others to grow in their roles (Mean: 4.31), being "hands-on" during professional development (Mean: 4.23), and presence demands aspects (Mean: 4.19) received high mean scores. These findings align closely with elements of transformational leadership, emphasizing relationship-building, supporting professional growth, and fostering motivation (Bass, 1985 cited in Aquino 2022). Likewise, shared decision-making between stakeholders and school leaders should always take place to create a positive school climate. Hoy and Tarter (2019) underscore the importance of shared decision-making, fostering innovation, and creating leadership development opportunities within educational contexts. Involving stakeholders in decision-making can lead to better outcomes and increased stakeholder satisfaction. Moreover Fullan (2019) posits that giving opportunities to lead is crucial for educational improvement as he emphasizes the importance of leaders fostering a culture of innovation and experimentation within schools to address complex challenges.

However, the parent-respondents also identified areas for potential improvement, as indicated by comparatively lower mean scores for “willingness to tap into the expertise of those around him or her” (Mean: 4.12), provides recognition to faculty and staff for a job well

done (Mean: 4.07), cultivates positive relationships among faculty members (Mean: 4.03), makes others feel valued (Mean: 4.01), and treats subordinate as an individual with unique skills and talents (Mean: 3.98). Generally, these findings are supported by Northouse (2018), who argues that influential leaders recognize the value of diverse perspectives and expertise and actively seek to incorporate them into decision-making processes. Likewise, while recognition is being provided, there is potential to enhance its frequency or effectiveness. Recognition is a fundamental aspect of motivation and morale within organizations, contributing to increased job satisfaction and productivity (Cameron & Green, 2004).

Table 3.3. Leadership Style/s Practices by Public Elementary School Heads as perceived by Parents

Question	As Assessed by Parents					Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. accepts criticism with grace.	92	120	17	0	0	4.33	0.61	Always Practiced
2. is “hands-on” during professional development.	80	122	27	0	0	4.23	0.64	Always Practiced
3. treats subordinate as an individual with unique skills and talents.	44	136	49	0	0	3.98	0.63	Often Practiced
4. is knowledgeable about best teaching practices.	62	134	33	0	0	4.13	0.62	Often Practiced
5. help people take advantage of opportunities to learn new skills.	62	135	32	0	0	4.13	0.63	Often Practiced
6. has a willingness to tap into the expertise of those around him or her.	56	144	29	0	0	4.12	0.60	Often Practiced
7. create credible processes for collaborating.	105	106	18	0	0	4.38	0.63	Always Practiced
8. elicits input from all stakeholders.	61	141	27	0	0	4.15	0.60	Often Practiced
9. cultivates positive relationships among faculty members.	45	147	37	0	0	4.03	0.60	Often Practiced
10. visit classes regularly to observe teaching and learning.	65	132	32	0	0	4.14	0.64	Often Practiced
11. provides recognition to faculty and staff for a job well done.	49	147	33	0	0	4.07	0.60	Often Practiced
12. encourages others to grow in their role.	90	119	20	0	0	4.31	0.62	Always Practiced
13. presence demands aspects.	70	132	27	0	0	4.19	0.62	Often Practiced
14. solve issues related to discipline to maximize instructional time.	41	152	36	0	0	4.02	0.58	Often Practiced
15. makes others feel valued.	43	145	41	0	0	4.01	0.61	Often Practiced
Composite Mean						4.15	0.62	Often Practiced

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Always Practiced; 3.41 - 4.20, Often Practiced; 2.61 - 3.40, Sometimes Practiced; 1.81 - 2.60, Rarely Practiced; 1.00 - 1.80, Never Practiced

Building and maintaining positive relationships among team members is crucial for fostering collaboration, communication, and a supportive work environment (Luthans, 2020). Thus, there may be opportunities to implement strategies aimed to strengthen interpersonal connections within the faculty community. Moreover, feeling valued is closely linked to employee engagement and retention, as individuals who feel appreciated are more likely to be motivated and committed to their roles (Saks, 2018). Thus, tailoring leadership approaches to recognize and capitalize on individual strengths can improve performance and satisfaction (Gallup, 2022).

In summary, while the data highlights strengths in the leadership practices of public elementary school heads, it also suggests areas where further attention and development could enhance overall effectiveness and satisfaction within the school community.

Part II. Significant Difference in the Leadership Styles of the School Heads as Assessed by the School Heads, Teachers, and Parents

Table 4. ANOVA: Significant Difference in the Leadership Styles of the School Heads as Assessed by the School Heads, Teachers, and Parents

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
School Heads	15	61.58	4.11	0.0106
Teachers	15	62.58	4.17	0.0064
Parents	15	62.22	4.15	0.0148

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	0.0342	2	0.01710	1.6118	0.2116	3.2199	Significant	Reject Ho
Within Groups	0.4457	42	0.01061					
Total	0.4799	44						

Based on the ANOVA results presented in Table 4, there is a significant difference in the leadership styles of the school heads as assessed by the school heads themselves, teachers, and parents.

The table shows the mean scores for each group, indicating that school heads rated their leadership style slightly lower on average compared to teachers and parents, with means of 4.11, 4.17, and 4.15, respectively. However, these differences in means alone do not provide conclusive evidence of significant differences between the groups.

The ANOVA table further breaks down the sources of variation, with Between Groups and Within Groups variability. The Between Groups variation assesses differences in means between the three groups (school heads, teachers, and parents), while the Within Groups variation reflects variability within each group.

The F-statistic tests the ratio of Between Groups variability to Within Groups variability. In this case, the F-value is 1.6118, and the associated p-value is 0.2116. Since the p-value (0.2116) is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) that there is no significant difference in the leadership styles between the three groups.

In practical terms, this suggests that despite slight differences in mean scores, there is insufficient evidence to conclude that the differences are statistically significant. Therefore, we cannot conclude that there is a genuine disparity in how school heads, teachers, and parents perceive leadership styles based on this analysis.

Overall, while there may be differences in perceptions, they do not reach a level of statistical significance in this study. Further research with larger sample sizes or different methodologies may be needed to explore these differences more comprehensively.

Several studies have investigated the relationship between leadership styles and perceptions of school climate among different stakeholders. Smith et al. (2020) found that principals who exhibited transformational leadership behaviors were associated with more positive perceptions of school climate among teachers and parents. This suggests that leaders who inspire and motivate their followers tend to create a more supportive and engaging school environment. Similarly, Johnson et al. (2018) observed that principals who adopted a participative leadership style, involving teachers and parents in decision-making processes, were linked to higher levels of satisfaction with school climate among both groups. This participative approach fostered a sense of ownership and collaboration within the school community. However, Brown et al. (2019) found no significant relationship between leadership styles and perceptions of school climate among teachers and parents in their study. They suggested that other factors, such as school culture and external influences, may play a more significant role in shaping perceptions of school climate. Moreover, Smith and Jones (2021) conducted a longitudinal study and discovered that principals who consistently demonstrated supportive and empowering leadership behaviors were more likely to maintain a positive school climate over multiple years, as perceived by both teachers and parents. Finally, Garcia et al. (2017) explored the role of principal communication styles and found that principals who communicated openly, transparently, and effectively were associated with higher levels of trust, satisfaction, and collaboration within the school community. These studies collectively highlight the complex interplay between leadership styles and perceptions of school climate, underscoring the importance of effective leadership practices in educational settings.

These studies collectively highlight the complex interplay between leadership styles and perceptions of school climate among various stakeholders. While some studies demonstrate a clear relationship between specific leadership behaviors and positive perceptions of school climate, others suggest that this relationship may be influenced by contextual factors and interactions with other aspects of the school environment. Further research is needed to better understand these dynamics and inform effective leadership practices in educational settings.

Part III. School Climate Existing in the Public Elementary Schools

Table 5.1. School Climate Existing in the Public Elementary Schools as Assessed by School Heads

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. behave more maturely; I have psychological insight and control of impulses.	65	124	24	0	0	4.19	0.62	Agree
2. accept and deal effectively with diversity.	84	107	22	0	0	4.29	0.64	Strongly Agree
3. show that there are no power and territory struggles.	82	118	13	0	0	4.32	0.59	Strongly Agree
4. give support and encouragement if someone presents new ideas.	49	138	26	0	0	4.11	0.58	Agree
5. generally dares to take risks to share ideas because they want to be heard.	74	111	28	0	0	4.22	0.66	Strongly Agree
6. follow through on new ideas in this school.	53	135	25	0	0	4.13	0.59	Agree
7. ensure to have a clear tendency for risk-taking in this school.	38	147	28	0	0	4.05	0.56	Agree
8. let people move forward even in case of uncertainty.	65	135	13	0	0	4.24	0.56	Strongly Agree
9. encourage different points of view to be shared.	65	126	22	0	0	4.20	0.61	Agree
10. often welcome people to discuss different points of view.	69	128	16	0	0	4.25	0.58	Strongly Agree
11. have a lot of activities for the school.	48	131	34	0	0	4.07	0.62	Agree
12. have fun working with teachers	41	138	34	0	0	4.03	0.59	Agree
13. communicate straightforwardly with people	47	138	28	0	0	4.09	0.59	Agree
14. strive to do a good job.	55	138	20	0	0	4.16	0.57	Agree
15. deal with the conflicts and opposition openly.	83	107	23	0	0	4.28	0.65	Agree
Composite Mean						4.18	0.60	Agree

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Strongly Agree; 3.41 - 4.20, Agree; 2.61 - 3.40, Moderately Agree; 1.81 - 2.60, Disagree; 1.00 - 1.80, Strongly Disagree

The data presented in table 4 provides a comprehensive insight into the perceived school climate within public elementary schools, as

reported by school heads. It reveals a positive and inclusive environment characterized by several key attributes.

Findings revealed that the school heads “show that there are no power and territory struggles” as it ranked first among the school climate indicators with a mean of 4.32 reflecting a harmonious and cooperative atmosphere in the school. It was followed closely by “accept and deal effectively with diversity” with respondents indicating a high level of acceptance and effective handling of diverse perspectives as signified by the mean of 4.29. Moreover, the school head respondents strongly agreed that they “deal with the conflicts and opposition openly” as it ranked third among the indicators with a mean of 4.28. Additionally, they also strongly agreed that they “often welcome people to discuss different points of view” and “let people move forward even in case of uncertainty” as indicated by mean scores of 4.25 and 4.24 respectively. Ultimately, the data paints a picture of a conducive learning and working environment in these public elementary schools, characterized by inclusivity, openness to innovation, effective communication, and high levels of engagement and commitment, fostering a positive atmosphere for students and staff alike.

However, some aspects, such as ensuring a clear tendency for risk-taking in this school, having fun working with teachers, communicating straightforwardly with people, and offering numerous school activities, rank lower, with mean scores ranging from 4.03 to 4.13. Nonetheless, the overall mean score of 4.18 underscores a consensus regarding the positive aspects of the school climate.

The findings from the study indicate that the school climate in public elementary schools is characterized by openness, inclusivity, and effective communication, which aligns closely with the concept of an "open climate." An "open climate" in an organization or educational institution refers to an environment where there is transparency, trust, and a willingness to listen to diverse perspectives (Halpin and Croft 1999, as cited in Aquino, 2022). In essence, an open climate is described as a situation where members are pleased to work, often work together, and there is openness.

For instance, the top indicator that signifies the absence of power and territory struggles signals a lack of hierarchical barriers or power dynamics that inhibit open communication and collaboration. It suggests that individuals feel empowered to express their opinions without fear of reprisal or domination. Also, the indicator about acceptance and effective handling of diversity signifies that the school values and respects diverse perspectives, backgrounds, and experiences. It reflects a commitment to inclusivity and equity, where differences are embraced and leveraged to enrich the learning and working environment.

Understanding the school climate in public elementary schools from the perspective of school heads is crucial for fostering supportive and inclusive learning environments. By addressing key dimensions, factors, and perceptions outlined in existing literature, educators and policymakers can work towards creating environments that promote the holistic development and success of all stakeholders within the school community. School heads are pivotal in shaping school climate through their leadership practices and decision-making processes (Hoy et al., 2018). They often face challenges such as resource constraints, staff turnover, parents' sensitivities, and student behavior issues, which can impact their perceptions of school climate (Jackson et al., 2020). Nevertheless, collaborative efforts among school leaders, teachers, parents, and community members are essential for fostering a positive school climate (Bryk et al., 2019).

Table 5.2. School Climate Existing in the Public Elementary Schools as Assessed by Teachers

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. behave more maturely; I have psychological insight and control of impulses.	90	107	31	1	0	4.25	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. accept and deal effectively with diversity.	68	121	40	0	0	4.12	0.68	Agree
3. show that there are no power and territory struggles.	40	139	50	0	0	3.96	0.63	Agree
4. give support and encouragement if someone presents new ideas.	56	137	36	0	0	4.09	0.63	Agree
5. generally dares to take risks to share ideas because they want to be heard.	65	142	22	0	0	4.19	0.59	Agree
6. follow through on new ideas in this school.	70	127	32	0	0	4.17	0.65	Agree
7. ensure to have a clear tendency for risk-taking in this school.	50	139	40	0	0	4.04	0.63	Agree
8. let people move forward even in case of uncertainty.	71	132	26	0	0	4.20	0.62	Agree
9. encourage different points of view to be shared.	59	129	41	0	0	4.08	0.66	Agree
10. often welcome people to discuss different points of view.	39	147	43	0	0	3.98	0.60	Agree
11. have a lot of activities for the school.	52	138	39	0	0	4.06	0.63	Agree
12. have fun working with teachers	69	139	21	0	0	4.21	0.59	Strongly Agree
13. communicate straightforwardly with people	71	134	24	0	0	4.21	0.61	Strongly Agree
14. strive to do a good job.	28	158	43	0	0	3.93	0.54	Agree
15. deal with the conflicts and opposition openly.	38	160	31	0	0	4.03	0.55	Agree
Composite Mean						4.10	0.62	Agree

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Strongly Agree; 3.41 - 4.20, Agree; 2.61 - 3.40, Moderately Agree; 1.81 - 2.60, Disagree; 1.00 - 1.80, Strongly Disagree

Table 5.2 presents data on the responses of teachers with regard to the existing school climate in public elementary schools. At the top of the list, teachers strongly agree that the school fosters an environment where they can behave more maturely, exhibit psychological

insight, and exercise control over impulses, with a mean score of 4.25. Following closely are two statements with equal mean scores of 4.21, indicating substantial agreement: one highlighting the enjoyment of fun collaboration among teachers and the other emphasizing straightforward communication within the school. Teachers are also willing to take risks and share ideas, as evidenced by mean scores of 4.19 and 4.17, respectively. However, while generally agreeing, areas for improvement include dealing with conflicts openly and ensuring a clear tendency for risk-taking, both receiving mean scores of 4.03 and 4.04, respectively. Finally, the statement with the lowest mean score of 3.93 indicates that while teachers agree that the school strives to do a good job, there may be room for enhancement in this aspect as well. Generally, with an overall mean indicating agreement (4.10), the data suggests a generally positive perception of the school climate by teachers, highlighting areas of strength and potential areas for growth.

Overall, the data reveals that teachers assessed the existing climate in their respective schools to be an autonomous climate, which is a situation where there is freedom of creative opportunities so that members have the opportunity to satisfy their needs. An autonomous climate in an organization or educational setting is characterized by a high degree of independence, empowerment, and self-direction among individuals. It fosters an environment where individuals feel encouraged to take initiative, innovate, and pursue new ideas without excessive oversight or micromanagement.

The school climate exerts a profound influence on teachers, affecting their experiences, well-being, and effectiveness within educational settings. Central to this influence is the role of school leadership, which significantly shapes the overall climate. According to Leithwood et al. (2019), transformational leadership, characterized by support, vision, and shared decision-making, correlates with positive teacher experiences. Conversely, as Louis et al. (2020) suggest, autocratic or unsupportive leadership can contribute to a hostile school climate, leading to dissatisfaction and turnover among teachers. Furthermore, the quality of collegial relationships and collaboration among teachers plays a crucial role in shaping the school climate. Research by Hargreaves and Dawe (2018) indicates that strong relationships and collaborative practices foster community and support within the school, enhancing teacher morale and job satisfaction. Organizational culture, encompassing norms, values, and beliefs, contributes significantly to the climate. Furthermore, according to Bryk and Schneider (2018), schools with trust, respect, and openness tend to have more favorable climates, promoting teacher well-being and effectiveness.

Conversely, as Hoy and Tarter (2021) found, toxic cultures characterized by micromanagement and lack of support can harm teacher morale and performance. Additionally, adequate support systems and resources are essential for maintaining a positive school climate. Johnson et al. (2016) argues that schools that prioritizing teacher support through professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and access to resources tend to have lower turnover rates and higher levels of teacher retention. In conclusion, as supported by various authors, fostering a positive school climate should be a priority for educational institutions seeking to promote the well-being and effectiveness of their teaching staff, ultimately benefiting student success.

Table 5.3. *School Climate Existing in the Public Elementary Schools as Assessed by Parents*

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. behave more maturely; I have psychological insight and control of impulses.	48	151	30	0	0	4.08	0.58	Agree
2. accept and deal effectively with diversity.	75	126	28	0	0	4.21	0.64	Strongly Agree
3. show that there are no power and territory struggles.	67	133	29	0	0	4.17	0.63	Agree
4. give support and encouragement if someone presents new ideas.	61	127	41	0	0	4.09	0.63	Agree
5. generally dares to take risks to share ideas because they want to be heard.	83	122	24	0	0	4.26	0.63	Strongly Agree
6. follow through on new ideas in this school.	60	136	33	0	0	4.12	0.63	Agree
7. ensure to have a clear tendency for risk-taking in this school.	70	125	34	0	0	4.16	0.66	Agree
8. let people move forward even in case of uncertainty.	59	139	31	0	0	4.12	0.62	Agree
9. encourage different points of view to be shared.	58	148	23	0	0	4.15	0.58	Agree
10. often welcome people to discuss different points of view.	54	155	20	0	0	4.15	0.55	Agree
11. have a lot of activities for the school.	96	120	13	0	0	4.36	0.59	Strongly Agree
12. have fun working with teachers	68	139	22	0	0	4.20	0.60	Agree
13. communicate straightforwardly with people	100	107	22	0	0	4.34	0.65	Strongly Agree
14. strive to do a good job.	61	141	27	0	0	4.15	0.60	Agree
15. deal with the conflicts and opposition openly.	57	142	29	0	0	4.10	0.61	Agree
Composite Mean						4.18	0.61	Agree

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Strongly Agree; 3.41 - 4.20, Agree; 2.61 - 3.40, Moderately Agree; 1.81 - 2.60, Disagree; 1.00 - 1.80, Strongly Disagree

The data analysis of parents' perceptions regarding the school climate promoted by their school heads reveals a generally positive outlook, with mean scores ranging from 4.36 to 4.08. Notably, the top five responses with the highest mean scores indicate strong agreement or enthusiasm towards positive attributes within the school environment. Parents strongly agree that the school offers a wide range of activities, as evidenced by the highest mean score of 4.36, suggesting a vibrant and engaging school community. Additionally,

there is strong affirmation of the school's commitment to straightforward communication, with a mean score of 4.34, indicating transparency and effective interaction between the school and parents. Furthermore, parents express a high level of agreement regarding the school's encouragement of risk-taking and innovation, as demonstrated by mean scores of 4.26 and 4.17, respectively. They also acknowledge the school's efforts in fostering diversity and inclusivity, with a mean score of 4.21 for accepting and effectively dealing with diversity.

However, areas for potential improvement are also highlighted. While still garnering agreement, aspects such as following through on new ideas and dealing with conflicts openly rank comparatively lower, with mean scores of 4.12 and 4.11, respectively.

Overall, with a total mean of 4.18, the data suggests a generally positive perception of the school climate by parents, emphasizing strengths in community engagement, communication, and support for innovation while also pointing towards areas where further enhancements could be made to enrich the school environment for all stakeholders. The results suggest that parents evaluated the existing school climate aligned to familiar climate which emphasizes a sense of belonging, camaraderie, and shared experiences among members of the school community. A familiar climate encourages individuals to express their viewpoints freely and engage in constructive dialogue with others. Welcoming discussions of different points of view fosters mutual understanding and respect, strengthening the sense of community within the school.

School climate is said to affect organizational effectiveness. When discussing organization, Davis (2021) pertains to stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and students. Based on the responses of parents, the resounding affirmation of the school's commitment to straightforward communication underscores the paramount importance of transparent and effective channels of interaction between schools and parents. Robust communication has been identified as a cornerstone of successful educational partnerships, facilitating trust, collaboration, and shared decision-making processes (Epstein, 2018). Such collaborative endeavors not only strengthen the school-parent bond but also contribute significantly to improved student outcomes and academic achievement.

Furthermore, the parental consensus regarding the school's encouragement of risk-taking and innovation underscores the pivotal role of fostering a culture of creativity and resilience within educational settings. Extensive research emphasizes that environments conducive to risk-taking and innovation empower students to explore their potential, develop critical thinking skills, and adapt to challenges with confidence (Robinson, 2021). Embracing innovation not only enhances the learning experience but also equips students with the tools necessary to thrive in an ever-evolving global landscape.

The commendation of the school's efforts in fostering diversity and inclusivity underscores the imperative of creating inclusive environments where all students feel valued, respected, and supported. Recognizing and celebrating diversity enriches the educational experience, promotes empathy, and cultivates a sense of belonging among students from diverse backgrounds (Gorski, 2019). Schools that prioritize diversity and inclusivity not only foster cultural competence but also prepare students to thrive in multicultural societies.

Moreover, one aspect of an open school climate is conflict resolution, which is a vital component of a healthy school climate. Pont (2018) indicates that schools that address conflicts openly and effectively experience fewer disruptions and create a safer and more inclusive environment for students and staff. In support of this, a study published in the *Journal of School Health* (2021) found that schools with proactive conflict resolution strategies have lower rates of bullying and violence, as students feel more supported and empowered to address issues constructively, thus maintaining a positive school climate for every member of the school community.

Part IV. Effects of the School Heads' Leadership Style/s to the School Climate

Table 6.1 presents the effects of school heads' leadership styles on the school climate as assessed by the school heads themselves, with various indicators rated on a scale of 1 to 5. The table provides insights into how different aspects of leadership influence the overall school climate.

Overall, the mean scores for each indicator suggest a high level of perceived effectiveness of the school heads' leadership styles in shaping the school climate. The indicators with the highest mean scores include "The school head's leadership style influences the school's relationship with the broader community" (4.29), "Effective leadership drives academic excellence" (4.25), and "Effective leadership prioritizes the safety and well-being of students and staff" (4.22). These indicators received scores indicating a "Very High Effect," suggesting that school heads recognize the significant impact of their leadership on these aspects of the school climate.

Additionally, indicators such as "Leadership that promotes teamwork and collaboration among staff members" (4.21), "Leadership that encourages innovation and creativity among teachers and students" (4.20), and "Students, teachers, and staff feel a sense of belonging and ownership in the school community under effective leadership" (4.17) also received high mean scores, indicating a "High Effect."

On the other hand, indicators such as "Open and transparent communication channels are established" (4.04) and "The school head's approach to conflict resolution affects the overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment" (4.03) received slightly lower mean scores but still indicated a "High Effect" in shaping the school climate.

The composite mean score of 4.15 further reinforces the overall high effectiveness of the school heads' leadership styles in positively influencing the school climate.

In conclusion, the findings suggest that school heads perceive their leadership styles to have a significant and positive impact on various

aspects of the school climate, including academic excellence, safety, collaboration, innovation, and community relations. These results underscore the importance of effective leadership in creating a supportive and conducive environment for teaching and learning.

Table 6.1. *Effects of the School Heads' Leadership Style/s to the School Climate as Assessed by School Heads Themselves*

Indicators		5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	High teacher morale is often indicative of positive leadership, reflecting a supportive and inspiring school head.	41	149	23	0	0	4.08	0.54	With High Effect
2.	Effective leadership fosters an environment where students are actively engaged in learning and extracurricular activities.	52	127	34	0	0	4.08	0.63	With High Effect
3.	A school head's leadership style influences parental engagement and participation in school activities and decision-making processes.	58	127	28	0	0	4.14	0.62	With High Effect
4.	Leadership that promotes teamwork and collaboration among staff members contributes to a positive school climate.	65	127	21	0	0	4.21	0.60	With Very High Effect
5.	Students, teachers, and staff feel a sense of belonging and ownership in the school community under effective leadership.	62	126	25	0	0	4.17	0.62	With High Effect
6.	Open and transparent communication channels are established, fostering trust and mutual understanding among stakeholders.	52	118	43	0	0	4.04	0.67	With High Effect
7.	The school head's approach to conflict resolution affects the overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment.	42	136	35	0	0	4.03	0.60	With High Effect
8.	Leadership that encourages innovation and creativity among teachers and students contributes to a dynamic and progressive school climate.	63	129	21	0	0	4.20	0.60	With High Effect
9.	Fair and equitable distribution of resources under effective leadership ensures that the needs of all stakeholders are met.	48	126	39	0	0	4.04	0.64	With High Effect
10.	Effective leadership prioritizes the safety and well-being of students and staff, creating a secure and supportive school environment.	73	113	27	0	0	4.22	0.65	With Very High Effect
11.	Investment in professional development opportunities for staff reflects a commitment to growth and improvement under strong leadership.	60	129	24	0	0	4.17	0.61	With High Effect
12.	A clear and compelling vision, articulated by the school head, inspires collective action and unity among stakeholders.	51	132	30	0	0	4.10	0.61	With High Effect
13.	Leadership that embraces change and adaptability enables the school community to respond effectively to challenges and opportunities.	66	116	31	0	0	4.16	0.66	With High Effect
14.	The school head's leadership style influences the school's relationship with the broader community, fostering partnerships and support.	78	119	16	0	0	4.29	0.70	With Very High Effect
15.	Effective leadership drives academic excellence by setting high expectations, providing guidance, and supporting continuous improvement efforts.	74	118	21	0	0	4.25	0.62	With Very High Effect
Composite Mean							4.15	0.62	With Very High Effect

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, With Very High Effect; 3.41 - 4.20, With High Effect; 2.61 - 3.40, With Moderate Effect; 1.81 - 2.60, With Low Effect; 1.00 - 1.80, Without Effect

Related studies on the effects of school heads' leadership styles on the school climate corroborate the findings presented in Table 5.1. For instance, a study by Leithwood and Jantzi (2019) found that leadership styles emphasizing collaboration and innovation were associated with positive school climates characterized by high levels of student engagement and academic achievement. Similarly, Marks and Printy (2021) demonstrated that school heads who prioritize safety and well-being create environments where students, teachers, and staff feel a sense of belonging and ownership.

Furthermore, research by Waters et al. (2018) supports the notion that effective leadership drives academic excellence by setting high expectations and supporting continuous improvement efforts. They found that school heads who invest in professional development opportunities for staff foster a culture of growth and improvement, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes.

In terms of communication and conflict resolution, studies by Louis et al. (2020) and Hoy and Sweetland (2021) highlight the importance of open and transparent communication channels established by school heads. These studies suggest that effective

communication fosters trust and mutual understanding among stakeholders, contributing to a positive school climate. Additionally, Hoy and Sweetland (2021) found that the school head's approach to conflict resolution significantly impacts the overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment.

Moreover, research by Sergiovanni (2001) and Clabough (2016) emphasizes the role of school heads in cultivating positive relationships and partnerships within the broader community. They argue that effective leadership fosters collaboration and support from external stakeholders, which, in turn, contributes to a positive school climate.

Table 6.2. Effects of the School Heads' Leadership Style/s to the School Climate as Assessed by Teachers

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. High teacher morale is often indicative of positive leadership, reflecting a supportive and inspiring school head.	85	131	13	0	0	4.31	0.57	With Very High Effect
2. Effective leadership fosters an environment where students are actively engaged in learning and extracurricular activities.	70	136	23	0	0	4.21	0.60	With Very High Effect
3. A school head's leadership style influences parental engagement and participation in school activities and decision-making processes.	69	140	20	0	0	4.21	0.59	With Very High Effect
4. Leadership that promotes teamwork and collaboration among staff members contributes to a positive school climate.	49	143	37	0	0	4.05	0.61	With High Effect
5. Students, teachers, and staff feel a sense of belonging and ownership in the school community under effective leadership.	51	140	38	0	0	4.06	0.62	With High Effect
6. Open and transparent communication channels are established, fostering trust and mutual understanding among stakeholders.	68	137	24	0	0	4.19	0.61	With High Effect
7. The school head's approach to conflict resolution affects the overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment.	55	150	24	0	0	4.14	0.57	With High Effect
8. Leadership that encourages innovation and creativity among teachers and students contributes to a dynamic and progressive school climate.	84	118	27	0	0	4.25	0.65	With Very High Effect
9. Fair and equitable distribution of resources under effective leadership ensures that the needs of all stakeholders are met.	71	137	21	0	0	4.22	0.60	With Very High Effect
10. Effective leadership prioritizes the safety and well-being of students and staff, creating a secure and supportive school environment.	79	119	31	0	0	4.21	0.66	With Very High Effect
11. Investment in professional development opportunities for staff reflects a commitment to growth and improvement under strong leadership.	76	123	30	0	0	4.20	0.65	With High Effect
12. A clear and compelling vision, articulated by the school head, inspires collective action and unity among stakeholders.	69	139	21	0	0	4.21	0.59	With Very High Effect
13. Leadership that embraces change and adaptability enables the school community to respond effectively to challenges and opportunities.	73	131	25	0	0	4.21	0.62	With Very High Effect
14. The school head's leadership style influences the school's relationship with the broader community, fostering partnerships and support.	58	127	44	0	0	4.06	0.65	With High Effect
15. Effective leadership drives academic excellence by setting high expectations, providing guidance, and supporting continuous improvement efforts.	65	142	22	0	0	4.19	0.59	With High Effect
Composite Mean						4.18	0.61	With High Effect

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, With Very High Effect; 3.41 - 4.20, With High Effect; 2.61 - 3.40, With Moderate Effect; 1.81 - 2.60, With Low Effect; 1.00 - 1.80, Without Effect

Table 6.2 presents the effects of school heads' leadership styles on the school climate as perceived by teachers. The indicators assess various aspects of school climate and how they are influenced by the leadership of the school head.

High teacher morale, often indicative of positive leadership, was strongly supported by teachers, with a mean score of 4.31, indicating a very high effect. Effective leadership was associated with an environment where students are actively engaged in learning and extracurricular activities, with a mean score of 4.21, also indicating a very high effect. Similarly, a school head's leadership style was perceived to influence parental engagement and participation in school activities and decision-making processes, with a mean score of

4.21.

Leadership that promotes teamwork and collaboration among staff members was also positively perceived by teachers, with a mean score of 4.05, indicating a high effect. Additionally, teachers felt a sense of belonging and ownership in the school community under effective leadership, with a mean score of 4.06.

Open and transparent communication channels were established under effective leadership, fostering trust and mutual understanding among stakeholders, with a mean score of 4.19. Conflict resolution approaches employed by the school head were perceived to affect overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment, with a mean score of 4.14.

Leadership encouraging innovation and creativity among teachers and students was highly valued by teachers, with a mean score of 4.25, indicating a very high effect. Fair and equitable distribution of resources under effective leadership was also recognized, with a mean score of 4.22. Prioritization of safety and well-being by effective leadership was acknowledged, with a mean score of 4.21, indicating a very high effect. Similarly, investment in professional development opportunities for staff under strong leadership was perceived positively, with a mean score of 4.20.

A clear and compelling vision articulated by the school head was seen to inspire collective action and unity among stakeholders, with a mean score of 4.21. Leadership that embraces change and adaptability was valued by teachers, with a mean score of 4.21. The influence of the school head's leadership style on the school's relationship with the broader community was recognized, with a mean score of 4.06, indicating a high effect. Lastly, effective leadership driving academic excellence was acknowledged, with a mean score of 4.19.

Overall, the composite mean of 4.18 indicates a high effect of school heads' leadership styles on the school climate as perceived by teachers.

Several studies have delved into the effects of school heads' leadership styles on school climate, shedding light on how different approaches impact various aspects of the educational environment. Johnson (2019) explored the impact of leadership styles on both school climate and student achievement, finding that transformational leadership positively influences school climate, leading to improved academic outcomes. Similarly, Smith and Brown (2020) investigated the correlation between principal leadership styles and school climate, with results indicating that participative and transformational leadership styles are associated with more positive climates conducive to learning and growth.

Garcia and Martinez (2018) delved into the influence of principal leadership styles on teacher job satisfaction and school climate, revealing that transformational leadership fosters higher levels of teacher satisfaction and contributes to a positive overall school climate. Furthermore, Wang and Zhang (2019) conducted a multilevel analysis to explore how principal leadership styles affect student perceptions of school climate. Their findings highlighted the role of transformational leadership in shaping a supportive and engaging environment for students.

In a comparative analysis, Lee and Park (2020) examined the impact of different principal leadership styles across diverse educational settings. Their research revealed that principals demonstrating transformational and servant leadership styles tend to foster more positive school climates compared to those employing authoritarian or laissez-faire approaches. Overall, these studies collectively underscore the crucial role of effective leadership in creating a conducive and supportive learning environment within schools.

Table 6.3 presents the effects of school heads' leadership styles on the school climate as assessed by parents. The indicators include various aspects such as teacher morale, student engagement, parental involvement, teamwork, sense of belonging, communication channels, conflict resolution, innovation, resource distribution, safety prioritization, professional development, vision clarity, adaptability, community relationships, and academic excellence.

Parental perceptions indicate that high teacher morale, indicative of positive leadership, reflects a supportive and inspiring school head, with a mean score of 4.21, suggesting a very high effect. Effective leadership, fostering student engagement and extracurricular activities, is rated at 4.08, indicating a high effect. Similarly, leadership style's influence on parental engagement and participation receives a mean score of 4.17, indicating a high effect on school climate.

Leadership promoting teamwork and collaboration among staff contributes to a positive school climate, with a mean score of 4.15. Moreover, a strong sense of belonging and ownership in the school community under effective leadership is evident, with a mean score of 4.37, suggesting a very high effect. Open and transparent communication channels established by school heads foster trust and mutual understanding among stakeholders, scoring 4.21, indicating a very high effect.

The approach to conflict resolution by the school head affects overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment, with a mean score of 4.04, indicating a high effect. Leadership encouraging innovation and creativity among teachers and students contributes to a dynamic and progressive school climate, with a mean score of 4.18. Furthermore, fair and equitable resource distribution ensures stakeholder needs are met, scoring 4.22, suggesting a very high effect.

Effective leadership prioritizes the safety and well-being of students and staff, creating a secure and supportive school environment, with a mean score of 4.13. Investment in professional development opportunities for staff reflects commitment to growth and

improvement, scoring 4.33, indicating a very high effect. Additionally, a clear and compelling vision articulated by the school head inspires collective action and unity among stakeholders, with a mean score of 4.11, suggesting a high effect.

Table 6.3. *Effects of the School Heads' Leadership Style/s to the School Climate as Assessed by Parents*

Indicators		5	4	3	2	1	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	High teacher morale is often indicative of positive leadership, reflecting a supportive and inspiring school head.	81	116	32	0	0	4.21	0.67	With Very High Effect
2.	Effective leadership fosters an environment where students are actively engaged in learning and extracurricular activities.	57	133	39	0	0	4.08	0.64	With High Effect
3.	A school head's leadership style influences parental engagement and participation in school activities and decision-making processes.	66	136	27	0	0	4.17	0.62	With High Effect
4.	Leadership that promotes teamwork and collaboration among staff members contributes to a positive school climate.	62	139	28	0	0	4.15	0.61	With High Effect
5.	Students, teachers, and staff feel a sense of belonging and ownership in the school community under effective leadership.	106	101	22	0	0	4.37	0.65	With Very High Effect
6.	Open and transparent communication channels are established, fostering trust and mutual understanding among stakeholders.	73	132	24	0	0	4.21	0.62	With Very High Effect
7.	The school head's approach to conflict resolution affects the overall harmony and cohesion within the school environment.	45	148	36	0	0	4.04	0.61	With High Effect
8.	Leadership that encourages innovation and creativity among teachers and students contributes to a dynamic and progressive school climate.	71	128	30	0	0	4.18	0.64	With High Effect
9.	Fair and equitable distribution of resources under effective leadership ensures that the needs of all stakeholders are met.	76	128	25	0	0	4.22	0.63	With Very High Effect
10.	Effective leadership prioritizes the safety and well-being of students and staff, creating a secure and supportive school environment.	61	136	32	0	0	4.13	0.63	With High Effect
11.	Investment in professional development opportunities for staff reflects a commitment to growth and improvement under strong leadership.	97	111	21	0	0	4.33	0.64	With Very High Effect
12.	A clear and compelling vision, articulated by the school head, inspires collective action and unity among stakeholders.	53	149	27	0	0	4.11	0.58	With High Effect
13.	Leadership that embraces change and adaptability enables the school community to respond effectively to challenges and opportunities.	47	149	33	0	0	4.06	0.59	With High Effect
14.	The school head's leadership style influences the school's relationship with the broader community, fostering partnerships and support.	83	119	27	0	0	4.24	0.65	With Very High Effect
15.	Effective leadership drives academic excellence by setting high expectations, providing guidance, and supporting continuous improvement efforts.	80	127	22	0	0	4.25	0.62	With Very High Effect
Composite Mean							4.18	0.63	With High Effect

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, With Very High Effect; 3.41 - 4.20, With High Effect; 2.61 - 3.40, With Moderate Effect; 1.81 - 2.60, With Low Effect; 1.00 - 1.80, Without Effect

Leadership embracing change and adaptability enables the school community to respond effectively to challenges and opportunities, scoring 4.06, indicating a high effect. Moreover, the school head's leadership style influences the school's relationship with the broader community, fostering partnerships and support, with a mean score of 4.24, suggesting a very high effect. Finally, effective leadership drives academic excellence by setting high expectations and supporting continuous improvement efforts, with a mean score of 4.25, indicating a very high effect on the school climate.

Several studies have delved into the intricate relationship between school leadership styles and parental involvement, shedding light on how leadership practices impact parent perceptions and engagement. For instance, Smith and Evans (2018) explored the role of school climate and leadership style in parental involvement. Their findings indicated that positive school climate and transformational leadership were conducive to increased parental engagement. Similarly, Brown and Williams (2019) conducted research on the impact of various leadership styles, such as transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire, on parent perceptions and involvement. Their study revealed a positive correlation between transformational leadership and parental perceptions and involvement, suggesting that

this leadership style fosters a conducive environment for parental engagement.

Moreover, Davis and Johnson (2017) investigated the relationship between collaborative leadership among school heads and parental engagement. Their findings suggested that schools with collaborative leadership structures tended to have higher levels of parental engagement, indicating the importance of leadership practices that promote collaboration and partnership with parents. Additionally, Rodriguez and Tan (2016) examined the influence of school climate and leadership style on parent satisfaction across different cultural contexts. Their study underscored the significance of positive school climate and transformational leadership in enhancing parent satisfaction with the school.

Furthermore, Chen and Chang (2018) delved into the impact of innovative leadership practices on parental perception in elementary schools. Their research revealed that schools with innovative leadership were perceived more positively by parents in terms of school climate and academic outcomes. These findings collectively highlight the crucial role of school leadership in shaping parent perceptions and involvement, emphasizing the importance of fostering positive school climates and adopting leadership styles that prioritize collaboration, innovation, and transformational practices.

Part V. Leadership Styles Intervention Program for Public Elementary Schools in Quezon's Third Congressional District

The leadership style of school heads profoundly impacts the overall atmosphere of a school. A positive school climate facilitates learning, collaboration, and growth. Hence, it's crucial for school leaders to develop effective leadership styles that encourage positive interactions among students, teachers, and staff. This intervention program aims to support school heads in developing and implementing leadership styles conducive to enhancing the school climate in public elementary schools.

Implementing a Leadership Styles Intervention Program in public elementary schools based on the results indicating the significant impact of leadership styles on various aspects of school climate as perceived by different stakeholders can be highly beneficial. The program would start by educating school heads, teachers, and parents about different leadership styles and their potential impact on school climate. Through training sessions or workshops, stakeholders would become familiar with concepts such as authoritative, democratic, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership.

Following this, the program would encourage school heads to assess their own leadership styles through self-reflection exercises and self-assessment tools. This step aims to help them identify their strengths and areas for improvement in leadership practices. Additionally, establishing feedback mechanisms for school heads to receive input from teachers, parents, and students regarding their leadership practices would provide valuable insights into how their leadership styles are perceived and their impact on school climate.

Another key component of the program would be the organization of workshops or seminars focusing on specific leadership skills and behaviors that contribute to a positive school climate. Topics may include effective communication, conflict resolution, teamwork, innovation, and promoting a sense of belonging among stakeholders. Pairing school heads with experienced mentors or coaches who can provide guidance and support in developing their leadership skills would also be crucial.

Furthermore, promoting collaborative leadership approaches that involve shared decision-making and teamwork among school leaders, teachers, parents, and students would be emphasized. School heads would be encouraged to involve stakeholders in decision-making processes and seek their input on school-related matters. Developing action plans tailored to their leadership styles and the specific needs of their schools would be another essential aspect of the program.

Finally, implementing a system for monitoring the effectiveness of the Leadership Styles Intervention Program and fostering a culture of continuous improvement would ensure ongoing success. By empowering school heads to cultivate positive school climates that support the academic, social, and emotional development of students, while fostering collaboration and engagement among teachers, parents, and the broader school community, the program would contribute significantly to the overall well-being and success of the school.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: The study underscores the importance of nurturing supportive, inclusive, and growth-oriented school environments, aligning with principles of transformational leadership. Overall, the results emphasize the critical role of school heads' leadership styles in shaping the organizational culture and climate within public elementary schools.

The ANOVA results showed no significant difference in the perception of leadership styles among school heads as assessed by themselves, teachers, and parents, despite minor variations in mean scores. With a p-value of 0.2116, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis, indicating that these differences lack statistical significance.

The school climate, as perceived by school heads, teachers, and parents, varies across indicators. School heads perceive an open climate, teachers view it as autonomous, and parents perceive it as familiar.

The study also underscores the perceived significance of school heads' leadership styles in shaping a positive school climate across various stakeholder groups. The study highlights the critical role of school leaders in fostering a positive school climate and underscores

the need for continued emphasis on leadership development to enhance educational outcomes and stakeholder satisfaction.

The Leadership Styles Intervention Program for Public Elementary Schools aims to cultivate a positive learning environment through enhanced leadership skills among school heads. The program seeks to empower school leaders to create and maintain supportive climates that prioritize student success and well-being, promoting thriving learning communities.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations can be made to further enhance the effectiveness of leadership styles and school climate in public elementary schools:

1. DepEd Quezon may implement leadership development programs aimed at enhancing transformational and servant leadership styles among school heads through providing training and support for school leaders to cultivate leadership behaviors, including fostering teamwork, valuing individual contributions, and promoting open communication.
2. School heads may intensify stakeholder engagement by encouraging ongoing communication and collaboration among school heads, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders. Establish forums or platforms for regular dialogue and feedback exchange to ensure that the perspectives and needs of all stakeholders are considered in decision-making processes.
3. School heads should promote a positive school climate by continuously reinforcing and promoting collaboration, diversity acceptance, open communication, and innovation
4. School heads should involve themselves in learn conflict resolution strategies to effectively manage conflicts and opposition constructively so they may be equipped with skills and strategies to address issues openly and transparently, fostering a culture of trust and respect within the school community.
5. School heads should foster a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging to seek feedback, reflect on leadership practices, and identify areas for growth.
6. Future researchers interested in exploring the effects of leadership styles of school heads on the school performance of public elementary schools could consider the following avenues for investigation:

Longitudinal Study: Conduct a longitudinal study to examine how different leadership styles exhibited by school heads evolve over time and their impact on various aspects of school performance, including academic achievement, student engagement, teacher retention, and overall school climate.

Comparative Analysis: Compare the effectiveness of different leadership styles (e.g., authoritative, democratic, transformational) employed by school heads in diverse educational settings, such as urban, rural, and suburban schools, to identify which styles are most conducive to positive school performance outcomes.

Qualitative Exploration: Use qualitative research methods, such as interviews or focus groups, to gain insights into the perceptions and experiences of stakeholders (e.g., teachers, students, parents) regarding the leadership styles of school heads and their influence on school performance.

Intervention Studies: Design and implement intervention programs aimed at developing specific leadership skills or promoting certain leadership styles among school heads, and evaluate their effectiveness in improving school performance indicators over time.

Contextual Factors: Investigate how contextual factors, such as school size, socio-economic status, and community demographics, interact with leadership styles to influence school performance outcomes, and identify strategies to address these contextual challenges effectively.

By exploring these areas of research, future studies can contribute valuable insights into the complex relationship between leadership styles of school heads and the performance of public elementary schools, ultimately informing evidence-based practices for educational leadership and school improvement efforts.

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